

Cover Domination value of Connected Graphs

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Abstract

Graph theory plays a vital part in real life applications like network design, network security, network monitoring, resource allocation, Facility location, location problems, network analysis like social network analysis, optimization problems etc. The domination concept designs effective and efficient networks where minimum number of nodes can dominate or control or regularize the entire network system. In network security system the dominating set can help the security resources strategically. In domination theory each vertex is capable of protecting the neighbouring vertices, it may be 1 vertex or 2 vertices or 3 vertices or..... $(n - 1)$ vertices. In this paper, we define a Cover Domination value (CDV) of graphs is used to determine the possibility of the number of vertices dominates two vertices is known as *2 – cover domination value* of G and is denoted by $dom^{2\alpha}(G)$, the possibility of the number of vertices dominates three vertices is known as *3 – cover domination value* of G and is denoted by $dom^{3\alpha}(G)$, and the possibility of the number of vertices dominates $n - 1$ vertices is known as *$(n - 1) – cover domination value$* of G and is denoted by $dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)$. And total of this covering domination value is known as *Total Cover Domination value* of a graph and is denoted by $T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}}(G)$ and the average of cover domination value of graph is known as *Average cover domination value* of G and is denoted by $CDV_n(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2}$, for $n = 3, 4, \dots, n - 1$. For the trivial graph covering domination value does not exist. Also found bounds for some standard graphs.

Key Words: Network analysis, adjacent vertices, covering domination value, total covering domination value

1. INTRODUCTION

A graph is a finite non-empty set of objects called vertices together with a set of unordered pairs of distinct vertices of G, called edges. The vertex set and the edge set of G are denoted by $V(G) = n$ and $E(G) = m$ respectively. A graph with n vertices and m edges is called a (n, m) graph. The degree of a vertex v in a graph G is the number of edges of G incident with v and is denoted by $deg(v)$. A graph G is regular of degree ' r ' if and only if every vertex of G has degree r . Such graphs are called r -regular graphs. A graph G is complete if every pair of its vertices is adjacent. A complete graph on n vertices is denoted by K_n . A bipartite graph is a graph whose vertex $V(G)$ can be partitioned into two non-empty subsets $V1$ and $V2$ such that every edge of G has one end in $V1$ and other end in $V2$; $(V1, V2)$ is called a bipartition of G. A graph is acyclic, if it has no cycles. A tree is a connected acyclic graph. In graph theory, some parameters have been studied widely such as connectivity, edge-connectivity, vertex covering edge covering and domination etc. These parameters are considered to protect the neighboring vertices. In a graph, every vertex is required to be protected and each vertex is capable of protecting every other vertex is called domination theory. A set $S \subseteq V(G)$ is said to be a **dominating set** in G, if every vertex in $V - S$ is adjacent to at least one vertex in S. The

domination number of G is the minimum cardinality taken over all dominating sets in G and is denoted by $\gamma(G)$.

2 - COVER DOMINATION VALUE OF CONNECTED GRAPHS

2.1 2 - cover domination value of graphs:

Definition 2.1.1: For any connected graph G , a 2 - Cover Domination value (CDV_2) of graphs is defined as possibility of the number of vertices dominates two vertices simultaneously is known as 2 – cover domination value of G and is denoted by $dom^{2\alpha}(G)$. The total of 2 – cover domination value is said to be Total 2 – cover domination value of a graph and is denoted by $T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G) = \sum_{i=1}^n dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_j)$. The average of Total 2 - cover domination value of graph

is known as Average 2 - cover domination value of G and is denoted by $CDV_2(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2}$.

Example 2.1.2:

For G , $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_2) = 4, dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_3) = 3, dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_4) = 4, dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_5) = 3, dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_3) = 3, dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_4) = 4, dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_5) = 3, dom^{2\alpha}(v_3, v_4) = 3, dom^{2\alpha}(v_3, v_5) = 3, dom^{2\alpha}(v_4, v_5) = 3$, thus $T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G) = \sum_{i=1}^n dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_j) = 33$.

Hence $CDV_2(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{33}{5C_2} = \frac{33}{10} = 3.3$

Remark 2.1.3: For any connected graph $G = (V, E)$, the total number of vertices that dominates each and every pair of vertices is the sum of internally disjoint paths of length 1 or 2

Remark 2.1.4: The number of possible ways to find $dom^{(n-1)\alpha}, n = 3, 4, 5, \dots, n$ of any graph $G(V, E)$ having n vertices and m edges is nC_r where $nC_r = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}$, the same formula is applicable everywhere used here.

Definition 2.1.5: For any connected graph G and $v_1, v_2 \in V(G)$ if v_1 and v_2 are adjacent then they dominate each other, so $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_2) = 1$.

Remark 2.1.6: $dom^{2\alpha}(G) = 0$ when $deg(u) = 1$

Theorem 2.1.7: For any connected graph G , the total number possibilities to dominate each pair of vertices is defined as

$$T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)} = \begin{cases} n + m & \text{if } G \cong C_n \\ n + m - 2 & \text{if } G \cong P_n \\ \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) = 1 \end{cases}$$

And the average of 2 covering domination value of the graph is obtained by $CDV_2(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2}$.

Proof: By remark 2.1.6, $dom^{2\alpha}(G) = 0$ when $\deg(u) = 1$

Consider $\deg(V(G)) \geq 2$

$$dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } v_1 \text{ is adjacent with } v_2 \\ 0 & \text{if } v_1 \text{ is not adjacent with } v_2 \end{cases} \quad (\because \text{by definition 2.1.5})$$

Consider $\deg(v_i) = 2, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ then $G \cong C_n$, then number of possibilities to get

$T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}$ is n times $2C_2$,

$$\text{ie, } dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_2) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_3) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_3, v_4) = \dots = dom^{2\alpha}(v_n, v_1) = 1 \\ = 2C_2$$

$$\sum_{i=1 \text{ to } n} \sum_{u \in V(G)} dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_{i+1}) = 1 + 1 + \dots + 1 = n \quad (\because \text{by definition 2.1.5})$$

$$= \sum_{u \in V(G)} [2C_2] = n[2C_2]$$

$$= \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2]$$

Also, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_3) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_4) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_3, v_5) = \dots = dom^{2\alpha}(v_{n-1}, v_1) = 1 = 2C_2$.

$$\sum_{\substack{u \in V(G) \\ i=1 \text{ to } n}} dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_{i+2}) = 1 + 1 + \dots + 1 = n$$

$$= \sum_{u \in V(G)} [2C_2] = n [2C_2] = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] \quad (\because (v_1, v_3)$$

are dominated by $v_2, (v_2, v_4)$ are dominated by $v_3, \dots, (v_{n-1}, v_1)$ are dominated by v_n)

And $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_4) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_5) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_6) = \dots = dom^{2\alpha}(v_{n-1}, v_n) = 0$

$dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_5) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_6) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_7) = \dots = dom^{2\alpha}(v_{n-2}, v_2) = 0 \dots$

That is, $\sum_{i=1 \text{ to } n} \sum_{u \in V(G)} dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_{i+3}) = \sum_{i=1 \text{ to } n} \sum_{u \in V(G)} dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_{i+4}) = \dots =$

$$\sum_{i=1 \text{ to } n} \sum_{u \in V(G)} dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_{n-3}) = 0$$

Hence $T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)} = \sum_{i=1 \text{ to } n} \sum_{u \in V(G)} dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_{i+1}) + \sum_{i=1 \text{ to } n} \sum_{u \in V(G)} dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_{i+2}) = n + n =$

$n + m$ (\because in $C_n, n = m$).

$\therefore \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m$ if $\deg(u) = 2$. Thus the average of 2 – cover domination value of graph is $CDV_2(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{n+m}{nC_2} = \frac{2n}{\binom{n(n-1)}{2}} = \frac{4}{n-1}$. For instance consider $G \cong$

C_4 , the number of vertices dominates both v_1, v_2 is 1, therefore, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_2) = 1$, the number of vertices dominates both v_1, v_3 is 2, therefore, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_3) = 2$, similarly its easy to find the 2 – covering domination value for the remaining vertices. Hence, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_4) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_3) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_4) = 2$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_3, v_4) = 1$, Hence $CDV_2(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{4}{3}$

By above theorem, $T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)} = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [deg(u)C_2] + m = 4[2C_2] + 4 = 8$ (\because in C_4 , 4 vertices having degree 2 and $m = 4$)

Thus, $CDV_2(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{8}{4C_2} = \frac{4}{3}$. Hence the theorem verified for the graph having degree 2.

Consider $G \cong P_n$, path with n vertices then number of possibilities to get

$T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}$ is $n - 2$ times $2C_2$, since $deg(v_1) = deg(v_n) = 1$.

By Definition. 2.1.5,

$dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_2) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_3) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_3, v_4) = \dots = dom^{2\alpha}(v_{n-1}, v_n) = 1 = 2C_2$.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{u \in V(G) \\ i=1 \text{ to } n}} dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_{i+1}) &= 1 + 1 + \dots + 1 = n \\ &= \sum_{u \in V(G)} [2C_2] = n[2C_2] = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [deg(u)C_2] \end{aligned}$$

Also, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_3) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_4) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_3, v_5) = \dots = dom^{2\alpha}(v_{n-2}, v_1) = 1 = 2C_2$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{u \in V(G) \\ i=1 \text{ to } n}} dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_{i+2}) &= 1 + 1 + \dots + 1 = n \\ &= \sum_{u \in V(G)} [2C_2] = n [2C_2] = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [deg(u)C_2] \end{aligned}$$

Since it is a path then $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_{n-1}) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_n) = dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_n) = 0 \dots$ (1)

Hence $T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)} = \sum_{u \in V(G)} dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_{i+1}) + \sum_{u \in V(G)} dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_{i+2}) = n + n - 3 =$

$(n - 1) + (n - 2) = m + n - 2$. Thus, the average of 2 – covering domination value of graph

is $CDV_2(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{n+m-2}{nC_2}$. For instance consider $G \cong P_4$, the number of vertices

dominates both v_1, v_2 is 1, therefore, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_2) = 1$, the number of vertices dominates both v_1, v_3 is 1, therefore, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_3) = 1$, similarly its easy to find the 2 – cover domination value for the remaining vertices. Hence, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_4) = 0$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_3) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_4) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_3, v_4) = 1$, Hence $CDV_2(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{5}{3}$

By above theorem, $T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)} = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [deg(u)C_2] + m = 2[2C_2] + 3 = 5$ (\because in P_4 , 2 vertices having degree 2 and $m = 3$)

Thus, $CDV_2(P_4) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{5}{4C_2} = \frac{5}{3}$.

Hence the theorem verified for the graph having degree 2.

Similarly, if $deg(v_1) = 3$ then then number of possibilities to get $T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}$ is $3C_2 +$ number of edges, if $deg(v_1) = 4$ then then number of possibilities to get $T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}$ is $4C_2 +$ number of edges and hence,

$$T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m. \text{ (since by definition 2.1.3).}$$

Hence, $T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m$. Thus $CDV_2(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2}$

Example 2.1.8:

For graph G_1 , $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_2) = 2$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_3) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_6) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_7) = 2$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_1, v_8) = 3$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_4) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_6) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_7) = 2$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_2, v_8) = 2$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_3, v_5) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_3, v_7) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_3, v_8) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_4, v_6) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_5, v_7) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_6, v_8) = 1$, $dom^{2\alpha}(v_7, v_8) = 2$. Hence $CDV_2(G) = \frac{23}{8C_2} = 0.82$

By above theorem,

$$T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G) = \sum_{v_i, v_j \in V(G)} dom^{2\alpha}(v_i, v_j) + m = 4(3C_2) + 2(2C_2) + 9 = 23.$$

(\because 4 vertices of degree 3, 2 vertices of degree 2 and $dom^{2\alpha}$ value does not exist for degree < 2).

$$\text{Thus, } CDV_2(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{23}{8C_2} = 0.82$$

2.2 3 - cover domination value of graphs:

Definition 2.2.1: For any connected graph G , a 3 - Cover Domination value (CDV_3) of graphs is defined as possibility of the number of vertices dominates three vertices simultaneously is known as 3 – cover domination value of G and is denoted by $dom^{3\alpha}(G)$. The total of 3 – covering domination value is said to be total 3 – cover domination value of a graph and is denoted by $T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1, k=1}^n dom^{3\alpha}(v_i, v_j, v_k)$. The average of 3 - cover domination

value of graph is known as Average 3 - cover domination value of G and is denoted by

$$CDV_3(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2}.$$

Example 2.2.2:

For G_2 , $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_3) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_4) = 2$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_5) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_3, v_4) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_3, v_5) = 2$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_4, v_5) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_2, v_3, v_4) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_2, v_3, v_5) = 2$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_2, v_4, v_5) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_3, v_4, v_5) = 2$. Hence $CDV_3(G_1) = \frac{14}{5C_2} = \frac{14}{10} = 1.4$

Remark 2.2.3: $dom^{3\alpha}(G) = 0$ when $\deg(u) \leq 2$

Theorem 2.2.4: For any connected graph G ,

$$T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G) = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_3] & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 3 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 2 \end{cases}$$

And the average of 3 - cover domination value of the graph is obtained by $CDV_3(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2}$.

Proof: For Graph G , $\deg(G) \leq 2$, it is obvious that $dom^{3\alpha} = 0$. Consider $\deg(G) \geq 3$. If any vertex is of degree 3 then there is only one possibility to dominate 3 vertices. ie, if $\deg(V(G)) = 3$ then $dom^{3\alpha} = 1 = 3C_3$. Consider a graph with $v_1 \in G$ having degree 4 is adjacent to v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 then the number of possibilities to dominate 3 vertices is $(v_2, v_3, v_4), (v_2, v_3, v_5), (v_2, v_4, v_5)$ and (v_3, v_4, v_5) . Thus, $dom^{3\alpha} = 4 = 4C_3$. The total 3 – covering domination value is obtained by summing up the number of possibilities of every vertex of G .

Thus, $T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G) = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_3] & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 3 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 2 \end{cases}$. The average of 3 – covering domination value is obtained by $CDV_3(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2}$.

Example 2.2.5: Consider the following graphs G_3 and G_4

In G_3 , $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_3) = 0$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_4) = 0$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_5) = 0$
 $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_3, v_4) = 0$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_3, v_5) = 0$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_4, v_5) = 0$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_2, v_3, v_4) = 1$
 $dom^{3\alpha}(v_2, v_3, v_5) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_2, v_4, v_5) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_3, v_4, v_5) = 1$.

Therefore, the 3 covering domination value of G_3 is, $CDV_3(G_3) = \frac{T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{4}{5C_2} = \frac{4}{10} = 0.4$

Using theorem 2.2.4, In G_3 , $T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G) = 4C_3 = 4$ and $CDV_3(G_3) = \frac{T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{4}{5C_2} = \frac{4}{10} = 0.4$

(since $dom^{3\alpha} = 0$ if $\deg(u) \leq 2$)

In G_4 , $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_3) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_4) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_5) = 1$
 $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_3, v_4) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_3, v_5) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_1, v_4, v_5) = 0$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_2, v_3, v_4) = 1$
 $dom^{3\alpha}(v_2, v_3, v_5) = 1$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_2, v_4, v_5) = 0$, $dom^{3\alpha}(v_3, v_4, v_5) = 0$

Therefore, the 3 covering domination value of G_4 is,

$$CDV_3(G_4) = \frac{T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{7}{5C_2} = \frac{7}{10} = 0.7$$

Using theorem 2.2.4, In G_4 , $T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G) = 4C_3 + 3.(3C_3) = 7$ and

$$CDV_3(G_4) = \frac{T_{dom^{3\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{7}{5C_2} = \frac{7}{10} = 0.7$$

Comparing G_3 and G_4 , $CDV_3(G_3) < CDV_3(G_4)$. Thus, G_4 is the preferred graph.

2.3 $(n - 1)$ - cover domination value of graphs

Definition 2.3.1: For any connected graph G , a $(n - 2)$ - Cover Domination value (CDV_{n-2}) of graphs is defined as possibility of the number of vertices dominates $(n - 2)$ vertices simultaneously is known as $(n - 2)$ - cover domination value of G and is denoted by $dom^{(n-2)\alpha}(G)$. The total of $(n - 2)$ - cover domination value is said to be *Total $(n - 2)$ - cover domination value* of a graph and is denoted by $T_{dom^{(n-2)\alpha}(G)} = \sum dom^{(n-2)\alpha}(v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n-2})$. The average of $(n - 2)$ - covering domination value of graph is known as *Average $(n - 2)$ - covering domination value* of G and is denoted by $CDV_{(n-2)}(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{(n-2)\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2}$

Definition 2.3.2: For any connected graph G , a $(n - 1)$ - Cover Domination value (CDV_{n-1}) of graphs is defined as possibility of the number of vertices dominates $n - 1$ vertices simultaneously is known as $(n - 1)$ - cover domination value of G and is denoted by $dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)$. The total of $(n - 1)$ - cover domination value is said to be *total $(n - 1)$ - cover domination value* of a graph and is denoted by $T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)} = \sum dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n-1})$. The average of $(n - 1)$ - cover domination value of graph is known as *Average $(n - 1)$ - cover domination value* of G and is denoted by $CDV_{(n-1)}(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2}$.

Remark 2.3.3: $dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G) = 0$ when $\deg(u) \leq n - 2$

Theorem 2.3.4: For any connected graph G ,

$$T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)} = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_{n-1}] & \text{if } \deg(u) = n - 1 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq n - 2 \end{cases}$$

And the average of $(n - 1)$ - covering domination value of the graph is obtained by

$$CDV_{(n-1)}(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2}.$$

Proof: For G is a trivial graph and vertex's degree is less than or equal to $(n - 2)$, it is obvious that $dom^{(n-1)\alpha}$ value is 0. Consider $V(G) = n - 1$. Then the number of possibilities is one. ie, $(n - 1)C_{(n-1)}$. For instance, consider the graph $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$, and v_1 and v_2 have degree 5. The number of possibilities to dominate 5 vertices simultaneously is $6C_5$ are

$(v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5), (v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_6), (v_1, v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6), (v_1, v_2, v_4, v_5, v_6), (v_1, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6), (v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6)$. Thus $dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5) = 0, dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_6) = 0, dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6) = 0, dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(v_1, v_2, v_4, v_5, v_6) = 0, dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(v_1, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6) = 1$ and $dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6) = 1$.

Hence, $T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)} = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_{n-1}]$ if $\deg(u) = n - 1$

$$\therefore T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)} = 2$$

Therefore, $CDV_{(n-1)}(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{2}{6C_2} = \frac{2}{15}$

Using theorem 2.2.4, $T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)} = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_{n-1}] = 5C_5 + 5C_5 = 2$, since $\deg(u) < n - 1$ is 0 and only two vertices having degree 5.

Therefore, $CDV_{(n-1)}(G) = \frac{T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{2}{6C_2} = \frac{2}{15}$

Corollary 2.3.4.1: For complete graph K_n ,

$$(i) \quad T_{dom^{2\alpha}(K_n)} = \begin{cases} \frac{n(n-1)^2}{2} & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 2 \end{cases} \text{ and } CDV_2(K_n) = n - 1$$

$$(ii) \quad T_{dom^{3\alpha}(K_n)} = \begin{cases} \frac{n(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)}{6} & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 3 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 2 \end{cases} \text{ and } CDV_3(K_n) = \frac{(n-2)(n-3)}{3}$$

$$(iii) \quad T_{dom^{4\alpha}(K_n)} = \begin{cases} \frac{n(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)(n-4)}{24} & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 4 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 3 \end{cases} \text{ and } CDV_4(K_n) = \frac{(n-2)(n-3)(n-4)}{12} \dots\dots\dots$$

$$(iv) \quad T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(K_n)} = \begin{cases} n & \text{if } \deg(u) = n - 1 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq n - 1 \end{cases} \text{ and } CDV_{n-1}(K_n) = \frac{2}{n-1}$$

Proof of (i) By theorem 2.1.7,

$$T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)} = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{For } K_n, \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m &= n [(n - 1)C_2] + \frac{n(n-1)}{2} \\ &= \frac{n(n-1)(n-2)}{1.2} + \frac{n(n-1)}{2} \\ &= \frac{n(n-1)}{2} (n - 1) \\ &= \frac{n(n-1)^2}{2} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $CDV_2(K_n) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{\left(\frac{n(n-1)^2}{2}\right)}{\left(\frac{n(n-1)}{2}\right)} = n - 1$

Proof of (ii) By theorem 2.2.4, For any connected graph G,

$$T_{dom^{3\alpha}(G)} = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_3] & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 3 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 2 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{For } K_n, T_{dom^{3\alpha}(G)} &= \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_3] = n [(n - 1)C_3] \\ &= \frac{n(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)}{1.2.3} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $CDV_3(K_n) = \frac{T_{dom^{3\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{\binom{n(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)}{6}}{\binom{n(n-1)}{2}} = \frac{(n-2)(n-3)}{3}$

Proof of (iii) we have $T_{dom^{4\alpha}(G)} = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_4] & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 4 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 3 \end{cases}$

For K_n , $T_{dom^{4\alpha}(G)} = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_4] = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [(n-1)C_4] = \frac{n(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)(n-4)}{1.2.3.4}$

Therefore, $CDV_4(K_n) = \frac{T_{dom^{4\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{\binom{n(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)(n-4)}{24}}{\binom{n(n-1)}{2}} = \frac{(n-2)(n-3)(n-4)}{12}$

Proof of (iv) we have $T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)} = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_{n-1}] & \text{if } \deg(u) = n-1 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq n-2 \end{cases}$

For K_n , $T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)} = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [(n-1)C_{n-1}] = n$ (since n vertices having degree $n-1$)

Therefore, $CDV_{n-1}(K_n) = \frac{T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{n}{\binom{n(n-1)}{2}} = \frac{2}{n-1}$

Corollary 2.3.4.2: For star graph $K_{1,n-1}$,

(i) $T_{dom^{2\alpha}(K_{1,n-1})} = \begin{cases} \frac{n(n-1)}{2} & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) = 1 \end{cases}$ and $CDV_2(K_{1,n-1}) = 1$

(ii) $T_{dom^{3\alpha}(K_{1,n-1})} = \begin{cases} (n-1)C_3 & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 3 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 2 \end{cases}$ and $CDV_3(K_{1,n-1}) = \frac{(n-1)C_3}{nC_2}$

(iii) $T_{dom^{4\alpha}(K_{1,n-1})} = \begin{cases} (n-1)C_4 & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 4 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 3 \end{cases}$ and $CDV_4(K_{1,n-1}) = \frac{(n-1)C_4}{nC_2}$

.....

(iv) $T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(K_{1,n-1})} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \deg(u) = n-1 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) < n-1 \end{cases}$ and $CDV_{n-1}(K_{1,n-1}) = \frac{2}{n(n-1)}$

Proof of (i) By theorem 2.1.7,

$$T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)} = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{For } K_{1,n-1}, \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m &= (n-1)C_2 + (n-1) \\ &= \frac{(n-1)(n-2)}{1.2} + (n-1) \\ &= \frac{(n-1)(n-2) + 2(n-1)}{2} \\ &= \frac{n(n-1)}{2} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $CDV_2(K_{1,n-1}) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{\binom{n(n-1)}{2}}{\binom{n(n-1)}{2}} = 1$

Proof of (ii) By theorem 2.2.4, For any connected graph G,

$$T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G) = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_3] & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 3 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 2 \end{cases}$$

For $K_{1,n-1}$, $T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_3] = (n - 1)C_3$

Therefore, $CDV_3(K_{1,n-1}) = \frac{T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{(n-1)C_3}{nC_2}$

Proof of (iii) we have $T_{dom^{4\alpha}}(G) = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_4] & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 4 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 3 \end{cases}$

For $K_{1,n-1}$, $T_{dom^{4\alpha}}(G) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_4] = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [(n - 1) C_4]$

Therefore, $CDV_4(K_{1,n-1}) = \frac{T_{dom^{4\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{(n-1) C_4}{nC_2}$

Proof of (iv) we have $T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}}(G) = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_{n-1}] & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 4 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 3 \end{cases}$

For $K_{1,n-1}$, $T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}}(G) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [(n - 1) C_{n-1}] = 1$ (\because one vertex is of degree $n - 1$)

Therefore, $CDV_{n-1}(K_{1,n-1}) = \frac{T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{1}{nC_2} = \frac{2}{n(n-1)}$

Corollary 2.3.4.3: For Wheel graph $W_{1,n-1}$,

(i) $T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(W_{1,n-1}) = \begin{cases} \frac{(n-1)(n+8)}{2} & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) = 1 \end{cases}$ and $CDV_2(W_{1,n-1}) = \frac{n+8}{n}$

(ii) $T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(W_{1,n-1}) = \begin{cases} \frac{n(n-1)}{2} & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 3 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 2 \end{cases}$ and $CDV_3(W_{1,n-1}) = 1$

(iii) $T_{dom^{4\alpha}}(W_{1,n-1}) = \begin{cases} (n - 1)C_4 & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 4 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 3 \end{cases}$ and $CDV_4(W_{1,n-1}) = \frac{(n-1)C_4}{nC_2}$

.....

(iv) $T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}}(W_{1,n-1}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \deg(u) = n - 1 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) < n - 1 \end{cases}$ and $CDV_4(K_n) = \frac{2}{n(n-1)}$

Proof of (i) By theorem 2.1.7,

$$T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G) = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) = 1 \end{cases}$$

For $W_{1,n-1}$, $\sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m = (n - 1)C_2 + (n - 1) (3C_2) + 2(n - 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{(n-1)(n-2)}{1.2} + 3(n - 1) + 2(n - 1) \\ &= (n - 1) \left(\frac{(n-2)}{2} + 5 \right) \\ &= \frac{(n-1)(n+8)}{2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } CDV_2(W_{1,n-1}) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{\binom{(n-1)(n+8)}{2}}{\binom{n(n-1)}{2}} = \frac{n+8}{n}$$

Proof of (ii) By theorem 2.2.4, For any connected graph G,

$$T_{dom^{3\alpha}(G)} = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_3] & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 3 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 2 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{For } W_{1,n-1}, T_{dom^{3\alpha}(G)} &= \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_3] = (n-1)C_3 + (n-1)(3C_3) \\ &= \frac{(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)}{1.2.3} + (n-1) = (n-1) \left(\frac{(n-2)(n-3)}{6} + 1 \right) = (n-1) \left(\frac{(n-2)(n-3)+6}{6} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } CDV_3(W_{1,n-1}) = \frac{T_{dom^{3\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{(n-1) \left(\frac{(n-2)(n-3)+6}{6} \right)}{nC_2} = \left(\frac{(n-2)(n-3)+6}{3n} \right)$$

Proof of (iii) we have $T_{dom^{4\alpha}(G)} = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_4] & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 4 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 3 \end{cases}$

For $W_{1,n-1}, T_{dom^{4\alpha}(G)} = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_4] = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [(n-1)C_4] = (n-1)C_4$ (\because only one vertex of degree $(n-1)$ and $dom^{4\alpha} = 0$ for the remaining vertices of degree equal to 3)

$$\text{Therefore, } CDV_4(W_{1,n-1}) = \frac{T_{dom^{4\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{(n-1)C_4}{nC_2}$$

Proof of (iv) we have $T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)} = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_{n-1}] & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 4 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 3 \end{cases}$

For $W_{1,n-1}, T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)} = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [(n-1)C_{n-1}] = 1$

$$\text{Therefore, } CDV_{n-1}(W_{1,n-1}) = \frac{T_{dom^{(n-1)\alpha}(G)}}{nC_2} = \frac{1}{nC_2} = \frac{2}{n(n-1)}$$

Corollary 2.3.4.4: For Bipartite graph $K_{n,m}$

(i) If $n = m$, $T_{dom^{2\alpha}(K_{n,m})} = \begin{cases} n^3 & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) = 1 \end{cases}$ and

$$CDV_2(K_{n,m}) = \frac{n^3}{(n+m)C_2}$$

If $n < m$ or $m < n$, $T_{dom^{2\alpha}(K_{n,m})} = \begin{cases} \frac{nm(n+m)}{2} & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) = 1 \end{cases}$ and

$$CDV_2(K_{n,m}) = \frac{nm(n+m)}{2 \cdot (n+m)C_2}$$

(ii) If $n = m$, $T_{dom^{3\alpha}(K_{n,m})} = \begin{cases} 2n \cdot nC_3 & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 3 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) = 1 \end{cases}$ and

$$CDV_3(K_{n,m}) = \frac{2n \cdot nC_3}{(n+m)C_2}$$

If $n < m$ or $m < n$, $T_{dom^{3\alpha}(K_{n,m})} = \begin{cases} n \cdot mC_3 + m \cdot nC_3 & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 3 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 2 \end{cases}$ and

$$CDV_3(K_{n,m}) = \frac{n \cdot mC_3 + m \cdot nC_3}{(n+m)C_2}$$

(iii) If $n = m$, $T_{dom^{4\alpha}}(K_{n,m}) = \begin{cases} 2n \cdot nC_4 & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 4 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 3 \end{cases}$ and

$$CDV_4(K_{n,m}) = \frac{2n \cdot nC_4}{(n+m)C_2}$$

If $n < m$ or $m < n$, $T_{dom^{4\alpha}}(K_{n,m}) = \begin{cases} n \cdot mC_4 + m \cdot nC_4 & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 4 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 3 \end{cases}$ and

$$CDV_4(K_{n,m}) = \frac{n \cdot mC_4 + m \cdot nC_4}{(n+m)C_2}$$

.....

Proof of (i) By theorem 2.1.7, $T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G) = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) = 1 \end{cases}$

For $K_{n,m}$,

If $n = m$, $T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(K_{n,m}) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m$
 $= (n + m)(nC_2) + nm = 2n \cdot nC_2 + n^2$
 $= \frac{2n \cdot n(n-1)}{2} + n^2 = \frac{2n^3 - 2n^2 + 2n^2}{2} = n^3$

Therefore, $CDV_2(K_{n,m}) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{n^3}{(n+m)C_2}$

If $n < m$ or $m < n$, $T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(K_{n,m}) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_2] + m$
 $= n \cdot mC_2 + m \cdot nC_2 + nm = \frac{n \cdot m(m-1)}{1.2} + \frac{m \cdot n(n-1)}{1.2} + nm$
 $= \frac{n \cdot m(m-1) + m \cdot n(n-1) + 2nm}{2} = \frac{nm(n+m)}{2}$

Therefore, $CDV_2(K_{n,m}) = \frac{T_{dom^{2\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{(\frac{nm(n+m)}{2})}{((n+m)C_2)} = \frac{nm(n+m)}{2 \cdot (n+m)C_2}$

Proof of (ii) By theorem 2.2.4, For any connected graph G,

$$T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G) = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_3] & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 3 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 2 \end{cases}$$

For $K_{n,m}$, $T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_3] = n \cdot mC_3 + m \cdot nC_3$
 $= n \cdot nC_3 + n \cdot nC_3 = 2n \cdot nC_3, \quad (\because n = m)$

Therefore, $CDV_3(K_{n,m}) = \frac{T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{2n \cdot nC_3}{(n+m)C_2}$

If $n < m$ or $m < n$, $T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(K_{n,m}) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_3]$
 $= n \cdot mC_3 + m \cdot nC_3$

Therefore, $CDV_3(K_{n,m}) = \frac{T_{dom^{3\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{n \cdot mC_3 + m \cdot nC_3}{((n+m)C_2)}$

Proof of (iii) By theorem 2.2.4, For any connected graph G,

$$T_{dom^{4\alpha}}(G) = \begin{cases} \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_4] & \text{if } \deg(u) \geq 4 \\ 0 & \text{if } \deg(u) \leq 3 \end{cases}$$

For $K_{n,m}$, $T_{dom^{4\alpha}}(G) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_4] = n \cdot mC_4 + m \cdot nC_4$
 $= n \cdot nC_4 + n \cdot nC_4 = 2n \cdot nC_4, \quad (\because n = m)$

$$\therefore CDV_4(K_{n,m}) = \frac{T_{dom^{4\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{2n \cdot nC_4}{(n+m)C_2}$$

If $n < m$ or $m < n$, $T_{dom^{4\alpha}}(K_{n,m}) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} [\deg(u)C_4]$
 $= n \cdot mC_4 + m \cdot nC_4$

Therefore, $CDV_4(K_{n,m}) = \frac{T_{dom^{4\alpha}}(G)}{nC_2} = \frac{n \cdot mC_4 + m \cdot nC_4}{((n+m)C_2)}$

The following corollaries are direct by the theorems 2.1.7, 2.2.4, 2.3.4

Corollary 2.3.4.5: For any regular graph G,

$$CDV_2(G) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} n \cdot [\deg(v_i)C_2] + m}{nC_2}, \quad CDV_3(G) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} n \cdot [\deg(v_i)C_3]}{nC_2}, \quad CDV_4(G) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} n \cdot [\deg(v_i)C_4]}{nC_2},$$

$$CDV_5(G) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} n \cdot [\deg(v_i)C_5]}{nC_2}, \dots, \dots, \quad CDV_{n-1}(G) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} n \cdot [\deg(v_i)C_{n-1}]}{nC_2}$$

Corollary 2.3.4.6: For any connected acyclic graph Tree T,

$$CDV_2(G) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} [\deg(v_i)C_2] + m}{nC_2}, \quad CDV_3(G) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} [\deg(v_i)C_3]}{nC_2}, \quad CDV_4(G) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} [\deg(v_i)C_4]}{nC_2},$$

$$CDV_5(G) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} [\deg(v_i)C_5]}{nC_2}, \dots, \dots, \quad CDV_{n-1}(G) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} [\deg(v_i)C_{n-1}]}{nC_2}$$

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